

Gerard Fox
The Visible Mind. Working Research
ORCID: 0009-0004-8589-7802

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The Common Good 2.0:
Appendix A. Visual Rhetoric

Conference Paper Extract
Practice-Led Research

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IN/DI/VISIBLE
Social Responsibility in the Age of
Entropocene

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Tischner University, Krakow, Poland
31 March 2023

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This foundational baseline establishes the "exponential decline of the commons" and probes universal education and participatory democracy as systemic solutions. Serving as the seed for all subsequent interventions, it contrasts the emotive visual provocations of 2023 against the dispassionate policy frameworks of 2025–2026. The 'Visual Rhetoric' extract documents the transition from diagnostic practitioner methodology to formal structural implementation.

Cluster 1: Systemic Collapse

P1–5 / Demonstrates the typographic methodology used to represent systemic overload; forcing the viewer to decipher interconnected crises beneath inverted imperatives.

Cluster 2: Dichotomies of Extractive Wealth.

P1–5 / Establishes the opposing systemic forces through unvarnished juxtaposition (hyper-consumption versus displacement; financial markets versus e-waste; isolated luxury versus ecological collapse).

Cluster 3: Rhetoric of Democratic Decline.

P6-10 / Maps the cultural symptoms of the Meta Crisis; moving from ecological philosophy into a visual critique of populism, culminating in a psychological diagnosis of extractive political leadership.

Cluster 04: The Emotive Civic Response.

P11–12 / Pivots from diagnostic despair to the affective reality of collective action; establishing the emotive foundation for the civic assemblies operationalised in subsequent research.

MONEY + BANKING

**WORLD'S
BEST
OVERSIGHT
ECONOMY
ENERGY**

17/11/2017

GROWTH FOR
GROWTH'S SAKE IS
THE IDEOLOGY OF
A CANCER CELL.

EDWARD ABBEY
ECOLOGICAL PHILOSOPHER

Swim

MOLS

0.50

0.50

0.50

0.50

THIRD ROCK FROM THE BOW

ARHLETT'S AT FT AGADU

Daily Mail

RETIRE, THEN PAY A CARE

CRASSER HORROR

STAR

Yes I've made mistakes. I have to live with it

IBUPROFEN IS RISK TO HEALTH

KIDNAPPED SOLDIER

FORGIVENESS THE CASE FOR

Some of the world's best... health with... health with...

The Daily Telegraph

COOP'S GUARANTEED

TO... CLUB

PERSONAL HEALTH

THE BRISH...

THE NARCISSIST'S PRAYER

THAT DIDN'T HAPPEN.
AND IF IT DID, IT WASN'T THAT BAD.
AND IF IT WAS, THAT'S NOT A BIG DEAL.
AND IF IT IS, THAT'S NOT MY FAULT.
AND IF IT WAS, I DIDN'T MEAN IT.
AND IF I DID, YOU DESERVED IT.

SUPRIYA MCKENNA

Democracy

**Citizen
Assemblies
Ireland**

62%

38%